

Faustwasm Package and Progressive Web Applications

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ABSTRACT

This paper surveys the latest developments in the FAUST web ecosystem, with a focus on modernization of its tooling and infrastructure. At the heart is the `faustwasm` project, which leverages TypeScript/JavaScript and WebAssembly to make it easier to build interactive, high-performance, and portable music applications. By adopting the Progressive Web App (PWA) model, the `faustwasm` project avoids the gatekeeping of proprietary app stores to deliver lightweight, cross-platform solutions that are easier to distribute.

Well-known projects such as SmartFaust and GameLan already use these advances, widening their appeal for participatory concerts and educational workshops. On a practical level, these apps turn smartphones into expressive instruments : built-in motion sensors capture gestures and translate them into sound instantly. Their plug-and-play nature, no special hardware or technical know-how required, makes them perfect for arts education and for introducing audiences to electroacoustic music.

1. NATIVE APPLICATIONS AND THEIR CHALLENGES

FAUST (Functional Audio Stream) is a functional programming language dedicated to real-time signal processing and synthesis [1]. Its core principle is to describe signal processors as mathematical functions operating on audio streams, which are then compiled into efficient C++, LLVM IR, WebAssembly, or other platform-specific code. This approach makes FAUST both highly portable and able to target a wide range of environments (desktop, embedded, mobile, and web).

For over a decade, the FAUST language has established itself as a powerful tool for building interactive musical applications, especially in projects harnessing the gestural capabilities of smartphones. Early projects like SmartFaust and GameLan, originally developed as native apps for iOS and Android, paved the way for innovative approaches to participatory musical interaction and educational outreach.

However, maintaining separate codebases for each mobile platform, alongside the demands of proprietary distribution

ecosystems like the App Store and Google Play, gradually exposed major drawbacks : increased development overhead, shifting validation requirements, and growing technical obsolescence. Meanwhile, the rapid evolution of the web, driven by technologies like WebAssembly, the Web Audio API, and Progressive Web Apps (PWA), has created promising alternatives. These modern web apps offer a user experience on par with native applications, but with significantly greater flexibility.

A complete architectural overhaul was launched to shift development toward a unified web-based model, more sustainable, accessible, and easier to maintain. Central to this transformation is the `faustwasm` project, which compiles FAUST code to WebAssembly and integrates with TypeScript/JavaScript wrappers. This approach achieves near-native real-time audio performance while significantly reducing the complexity of deployment and access.

Beyond the technical gains, moving to the web fosters a more inclusive environment for digital musical practices. The PWA format makes these tools ideal for a wide range of educational settings, classroom workshops, participatory art projects, cultural outreach programs, and more.

This article details this evolution, from the early days of native app development to the current web-based transition, highlighting both the artistic and educational benefits observed, as well as the technical and organizational challenges encountered. The migration of flagship projects like SmartFaust and GameLan to these modern, flexible platforms illustrates a broader ambition : to democratize musical expression and intuitive, gesture-based interaction through accessible, high-performance web technologies.

2. STATE OF THE ART

The use of smartphones and web technologies for interactive music creation has sparked numerous artistic and educational experiments over the past decade. This section reviews several approaches, ranging from native mobile applications to solutions directly built on web technologies.

2.1 Native Mobile Applications for Musical Creation

With the widespread adoption of smartphones equipped with motion sensors, many projects have explored their potential for gesture-based music interaction.

One of the most notable examples is *CoMo – Collective Movements*, developed by the ISMM team at IRCAM¹. This

1. <https://apps.ismm.ircam.fr/como>

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suite of applications leverages accelerometers and gyroscopes to support a range of use cases : artistic performance (*CoMo-Elements*), education (*CoMo-Education*), physical rehabilitation (*CoMo-Rééducation*), and choral conducting (*CoMo-Vox*). These apps rely on a centralized client-server architecture requiring WiFi connectivity and a dedicated network infrastructure, conditions that can pose logistical challenges.

The WAXML project by Hans Lindetorp and Kjetil Falkenberg at KTH [2] showcases a broad range of Web Audio-based smartphone applications designed for educational purposes². The demonstrations are particularly compelling, integrating multiple applications that extend the basic use of gyroscopic sensors. Notably, MediaPipe is used for facial expression, gesture, and skeleton tracking, enriching the expressive possibilities.

On Apple’s App Store, apps like *GyroSynth* transform the iPhone into a musical instrument inspired by the theremin, using device orientation to control pitch³.

These projects illustrate the diverse artistic uses of smartphones through creative repurposing of existing technologies. However, they often face limitations due to the need for platform-specific development and maintenance.

2.2 The Web as a Musical Platform

With the introduction of the Web Audio API and standards like WebAssembly, the web has gradually emerged as a viable environment for real-time sound synthesis and processing, paired with interactive musical interfaces.

As early as 2013, Roberts et al. [3] highlighted the browser’s potential as a musical platform, emphasizing portability, ease of access, and the absence of local compilation requirements. Their work helped pave the way for a new generation of tools and environments that leverage these capabilities.

A recent example is *WebChucK* [4], an in-browser musical programming environment based on the ChucK language. It showcases how domain-specific languages can now run dynamically within the browser, enabling rich and interactive sound programming directly on the web.

In a similar spirit, *Web Audio Modules (WAM)* [5] introduces a standard for building reusable audio modules in web-based hosts. Inspired by the VST plugin model, the WAM ecosystem supports collaborative development and modular reuse of complex audio processing components in an open environment. This approach has enabled full-fledged browser-based music production tools, as demonstrated by projects like *Sequencer Party* and other WAM-compatible hosts.

3. APPLICATIONS FOR MUSICAL OUTREACH

3.1 The SmartFaust Project

Conceived and developed by Christophe Lebreton in 2013, SmartFaust^{4 5}, is a series of musical smartphone applications built with FAUST for iOS and Android. These standalone apps are unique in that they rely exclusively on user gestures, rather than touch interactions on the screen, to generate sound. By leveraging the device’s motion sensors,

they transform smartphones into fully-fledged musical instruments.

In March 2014, during the Musique en Scène Biennale, GRAME organized a landmark concert showcasing this new form of interaction. Using SmartFaust apps, a large-scale participatory concert was held at Les Subsistances in Lyon, under the artistic direction of composer Xavier Garcia.

The performance unfolded in two parts. First, a series of works combined solo instrumentalists with a “choir” of smartphones operated by volunteers, musicians and non-musicians alike, who had been introduced to the tools during a preparatory workshop with the composer. The second part was a fully participatory piece involving the audience. Its distinctive feature was the immediacy of creation : no rehearsals, no prior musical training, just a smartphone and a designated “leader” to guide the collective performance.

This concert marked the beginning of SmartFaust’s role as a medium for engaging the public with electroacoustic music and computer-based musical creation.

4. APPLICATION DEVELOPMENT

SmartFaust applications were initially developed as native apps for iOS and Android, with a strong emphasis on achieving high real-time audio performance and low latency, particularly for motion sensor data, to ensure an optimal playing experience⁶.

4.1 Native Applications

Low-level development was structured as follows :

- **iOS** : The audio backend was built using CoreAudio⁷, with FAUST DSP code compiled to C++, and the app interface implemented in Objective-C using Apple’s APIs.
- **Android** : The audio backend used Oboe⁸, with FAUST DSP code also compiled to C++, while the app logic was written in Java. The backend was accessed via JNI (Java Native Interface), along with Android’s graphical frameworks.
- Sensor values (accelerometer and gyroscope) had to be retrieved using each platform’s specific APIs.

Once developed, the apps had to be submitted to proprietary platforms, Apple’s App Store and the Google Play Store, often a lengthy and restrictive validation process⁹. These processes aim to ensure compliance with strict guidelines, particularly regarding security and data handling.

4.2 Maintenance and Sustainability

In recent years, users have reported the disappearance of our apps from major download platforms, disrupting or even halting artistic and educational projects. As the hosting criteria for iOS and Android platforms continue to evolve, developers must continuously update their applications to ensure they remain available.

6. System-level latency is typically lower on iOS compared to Android.

7. https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Core_Audio

8. <https://github.com/google/oboe>

9. Because these apps rely mostly on gesture-based interaction and may lack traditional user interfaces, they were sometimes misunderstood during Apple’s review process, leading to time-consuming clarifications.

2. <https://waxml.org>

3. <https://apps.apple.com/fr/app/gyrosynth/id386527164>

4. <https://www.grame.fr/articles/smartfaust>

5. <https://github.com/grame-cnrc/smartfaust>

As web technologies matured, with the emergence of robust and reliable APIs such as the Web Audio API¹⁰, a complete reengineering of the technological stack was considered. This migration, outlined in the following sections, took place in several key stages.

4.3 Toward Web Applications

Using the web as a target platform offers several advantages. First, it centralizes development around a single codebase, eliminating duplication. Second, the web is inherently portable: a single application can run on any operating system or device without being tied to a specific proprietary ecosystem. Moreover, the combination of open standards and the fast evolution of web tools (WebAssembly, Web Audio API, PWA) now delivers performance and graphics capabilities comparable to native apps, while also simplifying distribution, updates, and user access.

Web platforms also offer built-in security guarantees that used to be manually enforced through app store validations. Modern browsers apply strict sandboxing policies that prevent web apps from accessing sensitive system resources without explicit user consent.

Additionally, features such as mandatory HTTPS connections and fine-grained permission handling (e.g., access to microphone, camera, or local storage) help provide a secure-by-default environment. Security policies that once required manual verification are now automatically enforced by the web ecosystem. Importantly, web technologies support forward compatibility, ensuring continued operation as standards evolve.

4.4 The faustwasm Package

Since 2014, FAUST DSP programs can be compiled into binary code for dynamic execution in web browsers using the Web Audio node infrastructure for sound rendering.

An early version of this effort relied on *asm.js*, a Mozilla-developed subset of JavaScript optimized for compiling C/C++ code to run efficiently in browsers. Through the Emscripten compiler¹¹, *asm.js* allowed near-native performance for computation-heavy web apps.

Starting in 2017, the advent of the WebAssembly standard¹² enabled a more stable and long-term transition of the FAUST toolchain to the web [6].

In 2022, a revamped web compiler was released as a standalone project named *faustwasm*¹³, with the Web Audio architecture rewritten in TypeScript. This package provides TypeScript/JavaScript bindings for FAUST DSP code, allowing the generation of standalone HTML pages, JavaScript modules (including WebAssembly binaries and other resources), and even integration of *libfaust* into apps that need to compile and run FAUST code on the fly.

4.4.1 Engineering Challenges

The construction of the library was not only a matter of porting FAUST to the Web platform, but also of addressing several engineering difficulties arising from the interaction between Web technologies and real-time audio requirements:

- The first layer is the FAUST compiler transpiled as

10. <https://www.w3.org/TR/webaudio-1.1>

11. <https://emscripten.org>

12. <https://webassembly.org>

13. <https://github.com/grame-cncm/faustwasm>

a WebAssembly library named *libfaust-wasm*. The C++ code is compiled with Emscripten and its API is exported using the Embind¹⁴ mechanism. The loader will take care of providing an instance of the *libfaust* WebAssembly module and of the associated virtual file system containing the DSP standard libraries (in a *libfaust-wasm.data* resource).

- The second layer provides FAUST compilation services, whose output is a raw WebAssembly module with an associated JSON description of the module.
- The third layer takes a WebAssembly module produced by the FAUST compiler or a precompiled module loaded from a file, and builds an instance of this module with the proper WebAssembly memory layout, ready to run.
- The fourth layer turns an instance into an audio node, with support for both AudioWorklet and ScriptProcessor nodes.

With this stack in place, the different upper-level components can be built. These components expose a unified and high-level API to developers, hiding the underlying complexity of WebAssembly instantiation, memory management, and AudioWorklet integration, and making it possible to deploy FAUST-based applications seamlessly across browsers, desktop, and mobile platforms:

- The *faustwasm* library enables the creation of both synthesis and effects audio nodes, as well as polyphonic instruments. It works in both Node.js-based environments and directly in browsers, and is published on NPM¹⁵.
- MIDI support is automatically activated when MIDI metadata is present in the DSP code, and is always available in polyphonic mode.
- Sensor data (accelerometer and gyroscope) is handled using a shared memory model¹⁶, which optimizes value transfer to the audio processing code (by completely avoiding memory allocations and the associated garbage collection model) and minimises latency.
- The Progressive Web App (PWA) model has been added for application deployment¹⁷.

4.5 The Progressive Web Application (PWA) Model

Introduced by Google in 2015, Progressive Web Applications (PWAs) are web-based apps designed to offer a native-like user experience.

They rely on caching and resource management via a Service Worker. On first access, all necessary assets are downloaded and stored locally. After this initial load, the app can function offline. Subsequent launches load the app from cache, ensuring smooth performance.

A minimal PWA setup includes:

- a Web Manifest (*manifest.json*) specifying app name, icons, theme colors, and display mode
- a JavaScript Service Worker that intercepts network requests and caches assets for offline use

14. https://emscripten.org/docs/porting/connecting_cpp_and_javascript/embind.html

15. <https://www.npmjs.com/package/@grame/faustwasm>

16. Supported on modern OS when served over HTTPS.

17. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Progressive_web_app

- a main HTML file delivered over HTTPS that activates the Service Worker

App updates can happen automatically when the Service Worker detects newer versions upon reconnecting to the network.

4.6 FAUST Progressive Web Applications

By combining FAUST, the Web Audio model, and other browser-native technologies, optimized audio algorithms can be executed directly in the browser, ensuring portability and the real-time performance needed for musical and interactive apps. Access to motion sensors allows immersive interaction, where user gestures dynamically control audio parameters.

4.6.1 Application Generation

A JavaScript architecture file uses the `faustwasm` package to load, compile, and deploy the DSP code as a Web Audio-compatible node, along with the `faust-ui` component¹⁸, which generates the graphical interface (also used in the Faust IDE¹⁹), and sets up the necessary infrastructure for PWA deployment.

From a DSP file, the `faust2wasm` script compiles the code into a wasm binary, generates a JSON description, and produces the associated architecture JavaScript file.

After installing the `faustwasm` package locally, a DSP program `foo.dsp` can be compiled using the command :

```
node faust2wasm.js foo.dsp foo -pwa
```

This compilation service is also integrated into web-based prototyping tools like the Faust IDE. Users can export directly by selecting “web” as the platform and “pwa” as the architecture, enabling immediate testing, for example on a smartphone via a generated QR code.

For final deployment, the necessary files (wasm, manifest, UI, etc.) can be produced using the “webaudiowasm” architecture and hosted on an HTTPS-configured web server, required for secure sensor access.

Controllers generated by FAUST can be linked to motion sensors via specific metadata²⁰ inserted into the parameter labels, such as `[acc:0 0 -10 0 10]` to describe the use of X-axis accelerometer values.

These parameters are parsed at app load time to set up real-time mappings between sensor values and musical parameter ranges. A few lines of platform-specific code are needed on iOS to explicitly request permission to access sensors.²¹

4.6.2 Application Publishing

Once the source code is written and compiled, the generated files (wasm binary, graphical assets, parameter JSON files, and PWA manifest) are organized into a dedicated directory and hosted on an HTTPS web server. This configuration is required by modern browsers to allow installation and execution of PWAs, especially for secure access to device sensors (accelerometer, gyroscope, microphone, camera, etc.).

A preconfigured `index.html` file and the accompanying JavaScript code ensure proper loading of the audio engine

18. <https://github.com/Fr0stbyteR/faust-ui>

19. <https://faustide.grame.fr>

20. <https://faustdoc.grame.fr/manual/syntax/#sensors-control-metadatas>

21. This is the only OS-specific behavior encountered during development.

and user interface. A QR code pointing to the app’s URL can be generated to facilitate installation on smartphones or tablets.

5. PORTING USING THE PWA MODEL

In 2024, SmartFaust and GameLan applications were ported to the new PWA architecture, allowing for real-world testing, debugging, and validation of this updated model.

5.1 Application Development

Existing FAUST code could be reused directly, with minor adaptations for handling audio files. Originally loaded as external C resources in 2013, these files are now managed via the built-in `soundfile` primitive in the web platform. The needed audio files are part of all the resources automatically loaded by the PWA model and kept locally in the web cache.

5.2 Application Deployment

The new applications were published in late 2024 using the GitHub Pages infrastructure²², with an open-source website built using MkDocs²³. When audio files are used in the applications, they must be manually added to the compilation output and uploaded to the server.

The website `faustpwa.grame.fr` hosts the SmartFaust and GameLan projects developed at GRAME. QR codes are automatically generated for each app. Figure 1 shows a PWA version of one of the SmartFaust applications.

Figure 1: *sfMoulin* from the SmartFaust project in PWA format : sound selection from a list and gesture-controlled transposition.

5.3 Limitations of the Web Platform

While the Web platform offers clear advantages in terms of accessibility, distribution, and cross-platform availability, it also introduces some drawbacks compared to native deployment :

- **Performance** : WebAssembly execution is generally close to native speed [6], but still depends on the efficiency of the underlying runtime (V8 in Chrome and SpiderMonkey/Cranefliff²⁴ in Firefox). This can lead to slightly higher CPU usage, especially for complex DSP chains, but performance remains acceptable for

22. <https://pages.github.com>

23. <https://www.mkdocs.org>

24. <https://cranefliff.dev>

the typical intended use cases, such as light to moderately demanding DSP algorithms.

- **Latency** : Audio callback timing in browsers is not as deterministic as in native environments such as CoreAudio on iOS or Oboe on Android. With the AudioWorklet model, the typical buffer size is currently 128 frames, but input/output latency can still vary depending on the operating system, browser version, and hardware.
- **Features and APIs** : Not all capabilities available in native environments are exposed on the Web. For instance, direct MIDI device access can be limited, and the use of certain sensors (e.g., accelerometer, gyroscope) is restricted or subject to additional user permissions compared to native applications.
- **Download size and startup time** : Although WebAssembly modules are compact, they still require downloading and instantiation in the browser or from the local cache. For complex applications, this may introduce a noticeable startup delay compared to native binaries.
- **Browser requirements** : Compatibility depends on relatively recent browser versions that support WebAssembly and the Web Audio API. Users on older systems may not be able to run the applications at all.

In practice, these limitations are often outweighed by the accessibility and zero-install nature of Web deployment, but they should be kept in mind when choosing between native and web targets.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Several of the developments presented in this work, including the implementation of PWA support, advanced motion sensor handling (accelerometer and gyroscope), and integration with the Web Audio infrastructure, were carried out in close collaboration with Shihong Ren.

As the lead architect of the FAUST IDE project, Shihong played a key role in modernizing the FAUST web ecosystem and making it more accessible for outreach and educational projects like the ones discussed here. This work was partially funded by the Metamorphoses project, an Erasmus+ KA2 European initiative (No. 2022-1-FR01-KA220-VET-000085833) focused on vocational training.

7. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The transition of FAUST applications to the Web, through the use of WebAssembly and the PWA model, represents a major step forward for educational and artistic outreach. This shift makes the tools more accessible, sustainable, and suited to a variety of creative and pedagogical contexts. It also promotes creativity, inclusiveness, and autonomy for participants.

An important next step is to enable the customization of the graphical user interface (GUI) using standard Web technologies such as HTML5, CSS, and JavaScript frameworks. The Web Audio module parameters and controls are exposed through an API and a JSON description, allowing developers to integrate alternative UI frameworks for rendering. This will enable educators and creators to design interfaces that are not only functional, but also visually engaging, adaptable to different devices, and tailored to specific artistic or pedagogical needs.

8. REFERENCES

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